

EFFECT OF REMOTE PLY ORIENTATION ON THE PERCEIVED MODE I AND MODE II TOUGHNESS OF θ/θ AND $\theta/-\theta$ INTERFACES

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ABSTRACT

Results are presented from an investigation of the effect of remote ply orientation on the perceived mode I and mode II toughness of a laminated graphite/epoxy. Experimental and numerical studies were conducted on four commonly used stacking sequences. Each sequence contained a midplane delamination and was subjected to bending loads that produced either predominantly mode I or predominately mode II conditions. Of the four sequences, two contained delaminations at 30/30 interfaces, and two contained delaminations at 30/-30 interfaces. For each interface type, one stacking sequence exhibited a relatively small transverse curvature under the applied loadings but a relatively large twisting curvature, whereas the other sequence exhibited a small twisting curvature but a large transverse curvature. For the two types of loadings (mode I and mode II), each of the four sequences were analyzed by three dimensional finite element analyses and were tested in precracked and non-precracked configurations. Using appropriate nondimensional parameters, the results of the study are used to make recommendations regarding the choice of stacking sequences for the determination of the toughness of arbitrary interfaces.

INTRODUCTION

It is relatively well-accepted that delamination growth in laminated composite structures can be predicted by comparing the energy release rate, G , to its critical value, G_c . For most laminated materials, G_c is a function of mode ratio and the relative orientations of the plies bounding the delamination [e.g., 1-5]. Most commonly, the double cantilever beam (DCB) test, as pictured in Fig. 1, is used to determine the mode I toughness (G_{Ic}) of unidirectional, θ/θ , or $\theta/-\theta$ interfaces [1,4]. For mode II, the end-notched flexure (ENF) test, shown in Fig. 2, is perhaps the most commonly used method. Other tests, such as the center-notched laminated beam (CNLB), have also been utilized [e.g., 2]. Both the ENF and CNLB have been used to determine the mode II toughness, G_{IIc} , of unidirectional, θ/θ and $\theta/-\theta$ interfaces [2-5]. However, despite the fairly large number of investigations (see for example, the reviews in References 2 and 4), there do not currently appear to be "accepted" test specimen stacking sequences for assessing the fracture toughness of θ/θ and $\theta/-\theta$ interfaces. Rather, two reasonably common general approaches appear to have emerged. In one approach, test specimens are comprised of primarily unidirectional plies [e.g., 1,2]; typically, the cracked regions are each composed of $[\pm\theta/0_n/\mp\theta]$ or $[\mp\theta/0_n/\pm\theta]$ sequences. This produces a specimen that is easy to fabricate and will exhibit a relatively small amount of transverse curvature during the test. The drawback is the relatively large bending-twisting coupling modulus of the cracked and uncracked regions. Alternatively, one may choose layups such that the cracked and uncracked regions are specially orthotropic [e.g., 4,5]. This produces specimens that will not exhibit any twisting during loading. The advantage is that the energy release rate (ERR) distribution is thought to be symmetric about the center line of the delamination front. The drawback in this case is the relatively

Figure 1. Double cantilever beam geometry.

Figure 2. End-notched flexure geometry.

large transverse curvature, and the accompanying non-uniformities in the ERR that result [6-8]. Unfortunately, one cannot choose a stacking sequence that eliminates *both* the transverse *and* the twisting curvatures. To the authors' knowledge, there has yet to be a study investigating the relative merits and deficiencies of the two specimen types.

In this work, results are reported from a combined numerical [9] and experimental study into this issue. Although the results are quite general, 30/30 and 30/-30 interfaces in a graphite/epoxy material were chosen for detailed study. For each interface type, two stacking sequences were chosen: one that exhibited small transverse curvature but large twisting curvature, and one that exhibited large transverse curvature and small twisting curvature. Specimens were tested in mode I using the DCB test and in mode II using the ENF test, and supporting three dimensional finite element analyses were performed for each specimen type for each type of loading [9]. Herein we concentrate primarily on the experimental portion of the study, where five precracked and five non-precracked Ciba-Geigy, C12K/R6376 graphite/epoxy specimens of each type were tested using each of the two test methods.

STACKING SEQUENCES

There are two primary issues to address when choosing stacking sequences for delamination testing of multidirectional specimens: elimination of the effect of residual thermal stresses, and minimization or elimination of three dimensional effects. The first issue is easily resolved by using specimens for which the two cracked regions and the uncracked region are all individually symmetric about their own midplanes. For specimens with a midplane delamination at a $+\theta/-\theta$ interface, this is not possible; however, anti-symmetric stacking sequences may be chosen for which the effect of residual thermal stresses on the ERR is negligible. Regarding the second issue, it is preferable to choose a stacking sequence for which the ERR and mode ratio are essentially constant along the delamination front. It has been shown that the effect of anticlastic curvature in DCB specimens causes the ERR to be highest at the center of a specimen and lowest at its edges [6,7]. Conversely, anticlastic curvature causes peak ERRs to occur at the edges of an ENF specimen [8]. The difference between the maximum and minimum ERR in either specimen has been shown [7-9] to correlate with a nondimensional ratio, D_c , defined as

$$D_c = D_{12}^2 / D_{11} D_{22} \quad (1)$$

This ratio was originally introduced in Ref. 6. For specially orthotropic plates, it measures the change in bending rigidity as the constraint condition changes from plane strain (for very short delaminations) to plane stress (for very long delaminations). In a previous work [8], it was suggested that $D_c = 0.25$ for the cracked regions is perhaps a useful "limiting value" in the design of fracture toughness test specimens. That is, specimens with D_c beyond this have markedly nonuniform G distributions and the "perceived" energy release rate and mode ratio, using conventional data reduction techniques, may be significantly different from the true result. Thus, the results from such a test are of little practical utility.

In addition to three dimensional effects caused by anticlastic curvature, bending-twisting coupling behaviors exhibited by the cracked or uncracked regions of a specimen will influence the ERR distribution. A recent study [9] indicates that specimens with large bending-twisting coupling moduli

(D_{16} and D_{26} in conventional notation [10]) will exhibit markedly asymmetric ERR distributions. The magnitude of this effect can be quantified by the B_t ratio, defined as [9]

$$B_t = D_{16}/D_{11} \quad (2)$$

where conventional notation is followed [10] and the coordinate systems are defined as in Figures 1 and 2. For a set number of plies, it is found that if stacking sequences are chosen to minimize one parameter (B_t or D_c), then the other parameter increases [9]. The stacking sequences chosen for the present study are at the two "extreme" ends of a number of practical layups that might be considered for use [9]; one layup minimizes B_t , but has a value of D_c approaching 0.25, the other layup minimizes D_c but exhibits a large B_t . The four layups and the abbreviated notation that will be used subsequently are presented in Table 1. In this notation, the " D_c " layups have the large D_c ratios and the small B_t ratios, and the " B_t " layups have large B_t and small D_c . All layups are 32 plies thick and contain a midplane delamination; the symbol "d" denotes the location of the delamination in the anti-symmetric layups. The values of the stretching-twisting coupling moduli, B_{16} and B_{26} , are essentially zero for the anti-symmetric layups, and all other terms in the 3×3 [B] matrices are identically zero. Both of the " D_c " type layups have D_c ratios, per cracked region, of 0.242, and B_t ratios per cracked region of 0.00. Both of the " B_t " type layups have D_c ratios per cracked region of 0.165, and B_t ratios of 0.0315. These values were obtained using the unidirectional ply properties of Table 2.

FINITE ELEMENT RESULTS

Fig. 3 presents three dimensional finite element (3DFE) results for DCB loadings of the two B_t type specimens. The geometry used in the models is the same as those used in the test program described in the following section. The horizontal axis in the figure is defined such that $y/B=0.0$ corresponds to one of the specimen's free edges, and $y/B=0.5$ corresponds to its center (cf. Fig. 1). The finite element model did not employ contact constraints near the edges of the crack front. Thus, the edge regions where $G_I=0$ in the figures is generally a region of crack face interpenetration in the model [9]. Each data point in the figure represents the energy release rate at the center of a local area of crack closure. Energy release rates in the figure are normalized by the total energy release rate, for the entire width, as determined by the 3DFE results. From Fig. 3, note that the ERR distribution for the $[\pm 30B_t]$ specimen is symmetric about $y/B=0.5$, whereas that for the $[\pm 30B_t]$ specimen is asymmetric. In view of the fiber angle and nature of the bending-twisting coupling, more load transfer occurs over the region $y/B \leq 0.5$ than in the other half of the specimen and, accordingly, the ERR is larger. As might be expected, the ERR distributions for both D_c type specimens were essentially symmetric about $y/B=0.5$ [9]. Very little difference was observed in the peak normalized ERR in the four specimen types. Hence, for a given interface type, there should be no appreciable effect of remote ply orientation on an experimentally determined G_{Ic} for the stacking sequences evaluated.

Fig. 4 presents 3DFE results for ENF loading of the $[\pm 30B_t]$ specimen [9]. The models used the same geometry as the test program described subsequently. Results are normalized to the total energy release rate for the specimen. As would be expected, the results for both the $[\pm 30B_t]$ and $[\pm 30D_c]$ specimens were symmetric about $y/B=0.5$; however, results for the $[\pm 30D_c]$ specimen were not. In this latter case, the asymmetry occurs due to the "local load path" provided by the fibers to the $y=0$ edge (cf. Fig. 2). Additional 3DFE results for the ENF loadings are presented in Table 3. The first row of the table presents the magnitude of the highest peak in total ERR divided by the average ERR, defined here as the value for the entire width. It is seen that the effect of high D_c appears to be "worse" than high B_t ; that is, the specimens with a high D_c and low B_t have higher peaks than those with high B_t and low D_c . This implies that crack growth from the specimen's edges is likely to initiate sooner in the former specimen types. The second row of the table presents the ratio of the peak ERRs for each specimen, defined as the total ERR, G_T , at $y=0$ divided by G_T at $y=B$. For the \pm layups, the ratio of peak ERRs increases with increasing B_t , whereas for the \pm layups, the ERR distributions are essentially symmetric and the ratio is very nearly 1.0. Thus, the \pm layups have a "preferred side" for the initiation of growth, whereas the \pm layups do not. The table also indicates that crack advance will be less self-similar in the $[\pm 30B_t]$ than the $[\pm 30D_c]$ specimen, and greater errors would be expected in the perceived ERR in this former specimen type when conventional data reduction procedures are followed.

Table 1. Geometries tested.

Specimen	Layup
[±30D _c]	[±30/0/-30/0/30/0 ₄ /30/0/-30/0/∓30] _s
[±30D _c]	[±30/0/-30/0/30/0 ₄ /30/0/-30/0/∓30/d/∓30/0/30/0/-30/0 ₄ /-30/0/30/0/±30]
[±30B _t]	[±30/0 ₁₂ /∓30] _s
[±30B _t]	[±30/0 ₁₂ /∓30/d/∓30/0 ₁₂ /±30]

Table 2. Unidirectional material properties for Ciba-Geigy C12K/R6376 graphite/epoxy.

$E_{xx} = 146.9$ GPa $E_{yy} = 10.62$ GPa $\nu_{xy} = 0.33$ $G_{xy} = 5.45$ GPa Ply thickness = 1.27×10^{-4} m

Table 3. Finite element results for ENF loadings (from [9]).

	[±30B _t]	[±30D _c]	[±30B _t]	[±30D _c]
G_T^{PK1}/G_T^{AVG}	5.771	6.934	3.087	3.830
G_T^{PK1}/G_T^{PK2}	3.656	3.386	1.001	1.001

Figure 3. Finite element results for DCB.

Figure 4. Finite element results for ENF.

DOUBLE CANTILEVER BEAM: TEST PROCEDURE AND DATA REDUCTION

All of the DCB specimens were 2.54 cm wide, contained a 12.7 μ m thick preimplanted teflon starter crack, and had an initial crack length of approximately 5.72 cm. As shown in Figure 1, loading blocks were used to prevent any possible introduction of end moments. All precracking was done within the loading fixture by simply advancing the crack a small amount. All specimens were loaded under displacement control at a rate of 0.75 mm/min. Interestingly, unidirectional specimens of this material exhibited "stick-slip" type growth [4], but all of the layups tested in this study exhibited slow, stable

crack advance. After a noticeable increment of crack advance, specimens were partially unloaded, and then reloaded until a peak in the load was observed. This was taken to be the critical load, P_c , and was recorded along with the associated critical deflection, δ_c . The new crack length would then be recorded as the average of the readings at either edge, and the process repeated.

The mode I fracture toughness was found by compliance calibration using the equation [11]

$$G = \frac{P^2}{2B} \frac{\partial C}{\partial a} \quad (3)$$

Here, B is the specimen's width and C is the compliance. Compliance as a function of crack length was found for each specimen from the slope of the load-deflection data. The method of least squares was used to curve-fit these points and to obtain the coefficients R and n in the equation [12]

$$C = Ra^n \quad (4)$$

Substituting (4) into (3) yields

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{nP_c \delta_c}{2Ba} \quad (5)$$

where P_c and δ_c are the load and deflection, respectively, at the onset of crack advance.

END-NOTCHED FLEXURE: TEST PROCEDURE AND DATA REDUCTION

The procedure described in Ref. 8 was used to determine the crack length, a , and half-span length, L , for the ENF specimens (cf. Fig. 2). This procedure is intended to eliminate geometric nonlinearities and to minimize the effect of shear deformations on the energy release rate. This latter minimization is desirable if one wishes to use a classical plate theory based method of data reduction [4,5,8]. Application of the procedure resulted in a crack length of 31.75 mm, a half-span length of 63.50 mm, and a width of 2.54 cm for all specimen types. Considerably more detail on choosing geometries for testing multidirectional ENF specimens is included in References 5 and 8. All specimens contained a 12.7 μ m thick preimplanted teflon starter crack.

All ENF specimens were loaded continuously in displacement control at a rate of 1.5 mm/min, and data reduction was performed by compliance calibration. A compliance versus crack length curve was developed for each specimen tested. To this end, each specimen was loaded to approximately 50% of its predicted fracture load at five different crack lengths. These included the crack length at which the fracture test was to be performed, \bar{a} (31.75 mm for all specimens), $\bar{a} \pm 5.08$ mm, and $\bar{a} \pm 10.16$ mm. The crack length was adjusted by placing the specimen appropriately into the testing fixture. At any given crack length, the compliance was obtained from the slope of a linear least-squares curve fit of the deflection versus load data. Next, a compliance versus crack length curve was obtained, for each specimen, by fitting a cubic polynomial of the form

$$C = C_0 + C_1a + C_2a^2 + C_3a^3 \quad (6)$$

to the compliance versus crack length data. This procedure was utilized, rather than using a single compliance curve for all specimens, because previous work has indicated significant specimen-to-specimen variation may be masked by this latter approach [5]. Also, we point out that other expressions are typically used to fit compliance data from the ENF test [e.g.,13]. For example, the second and often the first order term in the polynomial expression may be excluded. It is our approach to obtain the best numerical fit of the data possible; if any of the intermediate order terms are unimportant, we assume that this will be reflected in the values of the coefficients as obtained by our curve fitting procedure. Once the compliance versus crack length relations were obtained for each specimen, all specimens were loaded to fracture. G_{IIc} for each specimen was obtained by substituting the appropriate compliance calibration curve, Eqn (6), into Eqn (3) and evaluating the resulting expression at the critical load, P_c .

Precracking of the ENF specimens was performed in mode II within the ENF fixture. However, a clamp was used to limit the amount of crack advance during the process. The clamp had a lower surface that was flat and coated with a thin sheet of rubber, and an upper surface comprised of a captive 6.35 mm diameter dowel pin. The clamp would be positioned such that the center of the dowel pin was 3.2 mm ahead of the crack tip. It was observed that precracking with large a/L , where crack advance is stable under displacement control, often produced delamination fronts that were not straight, whereas small a/L , where crack advance is unstable, generally produced the desired result. Following some trial and error evaluations, all ENF specimens were precracked at $a/L \approx 0.56$. All precracking was performed in displacement control, and the load versus deflection curve was monitored in real-time. The test was stopped as soon as any nonlinearity was evident, at which time the specimen would be removed from the loading fixture and ultrasonically inspected. If: (1) crack advance had occurred across the entire width of the specimen; (2) the crack front was essentially straight, defined by us as the leading point on the crack front was not more than 0.25 cm ahead of the lagging point; and (3) no interface shifting had occurred, then the specimen was "approved" for subsequent testing. If condition (3) was satisfied, but either of (1) or (2) were not, then the process was repeated. Depending on the amount of crack advance, this may or may not have involved a repositioning of the clamp. This iterative procedure continued until either the specimen met our 3 criteria for acceptance, or until more than 10% of the delamination front shifted interfaces. When this latter event occurred, the specimen was "not approved" and was not tested.

The above procedure worked quite well for the all but the $[\pm 30B_1]$ specimens. For these specimen types, growth virtually always initiated at $y=0$, where the ERR concentrations are the most pronounced (cf. Figures 2 and 4). The other edge, at $y=B$, would not advance at all until several precrack "iterations" had been performed. Most times, when this edge finally did advance, the local delamination front would immediately shift upwards one interface. Thus, we were forced to first precrack these specimens until most of the front had advanced in mode II. The resulting configuration would appear as in Fig. 5. Next, the teflon used to manufacture the crack would carefully be removed [4], the precracking clamp would be placed across the delamination front, and a wedge would be used along one edge of the specimen only to advance the lagging portion of the front in mode I. The resulting delamination fronts were found to meet the criteria for straightness and percentage of interface shift.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS: DOUBLE CANTILEVER BEAM

All of the DCB specimens exhibited linear load versus deflection response prior to fracture. For all specimens, precracked and non-precracked results presented herein are from the same specimen. Non-precracked toughnesses are taken to be the value of G_{Ic} for initiation from the teflon starter crack, and precracked toughnesses are taken to be the value of G_{Ic} from this newly created crack front. This provides an obvious reduction in the number of specimens required. All the non-precracked toughnesses were taken from the first load drop observed in the load versus deflection plot. In many cases, this corresponded to crack advance only in the center region of the specimen and was not accompanied by any measurable advance along the specimen's edges. When this occurred, a "modified" data reduction procedure was used. Since the first and second increment of crack growth occurred at the same crack length, equations (3)-(5), used with all data, will not give accurate results for these first two points. Thus, to obtain the non-precracked toughness, the second increment of crack advance was ignored when performing the curve-fits. To obtain the precracked toughness, the first increment of crack advance was ignored during the curve-fitting procedure.

Fig. 6 presents a bar chart of all of the precracked and non-precracked data. The ends of the bars represent the sample mean, and the two ends of the "error bars" are at the plus one and minus one normal standard deviation values. For both of the \pm specimen types, precracked toughnesses are approximately 4% lower than the non-precracked values, whereas precracked and non-precracked toughnesses are essentially the

Figure 5. Delamination front shape for $[\pm 30B_1]$ specimen after mode II precracking.

same for the \pm specimen types. Delamination surface markings indicated that the delamination front changed shape dramatically during the first increment of crack advance, from the straight front created by the teflon starter crack to a considerably curved shape. Despite the measures taken, this non-self-similar crack advance will affect the accuracy of the data reduction procedure. It is likely that if a true accounting was made of the potential energy loss divided by the surface area created, non-precracked toughnesses would be observed to be larger than the precracked value. This has been observed for all other interfaces tested in this material, as well as for other graphite/epoxies [4]. It is interesting to note that the initiation toughness of all 4 interfaces is *below* that for a precracked, unidirectional specimen, for which an average toughness of 274 J/m^2 has been observed [4].

Figure 6. Experimental results from DCB tests.

Despite the agreement in initiation toughness between the 4 layups, their resistance (R) curve behaviors were markedly different. Both of the \pm layups exhibited relatively shallow R (G_{IC} vs. a) curves, and the delamination surfaces of these specimens were reasonably smooth and planar. The maximum value of G_{IC} in either of these specimen types was approximately 275 J/m^2 . The R curves of the \pm specimens were relatively steep, with the increase in G_c more pronounced in the $[\pm 30B_c]$ than the $[\pm 30D_c]$ specimen; in the former case, peak G_{IC} values were on the order of 440 J/m^2 , and in the latter case were on the order of 400 J/m^2 . Delamination surfaces in both of these specimen types were extremely rough, multiplanar, and contained fibers from both of the plies that bounded the interface.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS: END-NOTCHED FLEXURE

The load versus deflection plots from the ENF tests of all specimens showed a small amount of nonlinearity that initiated at a center-point deflection of approximately 2.5 mm. This is illustrated in Fig. 7, which shows load-deflection plots of four non-precracked specimens. A detailed investigation [4] indicated that the nonlinearity was due to geometric effects, rather than crack tip plastic deformation [3] or subcritical crack advance [5]. However, since the amount of nonlinearity is small, it likely does not have a significant effect on the critical strain energy release rate. Thus, in what follows, all toughness values are obtained from the peak in the load versus deflection curves, and the small effect of the geometric nonlinearity on G_{IIc} is ignored.

Figure 8 presents all of the non-precracked and precracked ENF results. The chart is similar to that of Fig. 6; the mean and plus and minus one normal standard deviation values are shown. Unlike the DCB, the precracked toughnesses are seen to be significantly lower than the non-precracked values.

Figure 7. Load-deflection plots from ENF.

Figure 8. Experimental results from ENF tests.

Aside from this, this figure shows that there is clearly no significant effect of stacking sequence on toughness for the two sequences evaluated for each interface type. In addition, there is not a significant difference in toughness between the \dagger and \pm interfaces. These same conclusions have been reached in other studies for this material for a range of interfaces [4,5].

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of this investigation and the supporting numerical study [9] can be used to make some general recommendations regarding the choice of stacking sequences for fracture toughness test specimens. First, previous results [5,8] indicate that the D_c ratio, per cracked region, should always be below 0.25. Otherwise, the effect of anticlastic curvature on the ERR and mode ratio distributions is so pronounced that two-dimensional analyses and data reduction procedures will produce significant errors. The results presented herein suggest that for high mode I tests, high B_t ratio specimens are acceptable. However, with increasing amounts of mode II, the effect of the bending-twisting coupling on precracking becomes pronounced. Thus, for high mode II testing, it is preferable to use a high D_c ratio specimen with low B_t , rather than the reverse. This will allow precracking at the mode ratio of interest to be performed in a relatively simple manner, crack growth from the precrack will be self-similar, and accurate results will be obtained. For certain interfaces, such as 45/45 or 45/-45, it is likely that a test specimen for which $D_c \leq 0.25$ and $B_t \approx 0$ will require a large number of plies. In these instances, once the number of plies is fixed, it would likely be best to choose stacking sequences such that $D_c \leq 0.25$ and, within this constraint, that B_t is a minimum. A number of sample sequences of this type are presented in Ref. 9.

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